

Measurement of Ion Activities in Clay Suspension by Membrane Electrode

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H⁺, Na⁺, Ca⁺² ion activities in clay suspension obtained from two different soils have been measured by means of a resin membrane electrode and the data interpreted.

Clay suspensions are slightly ionised as has been shown from measurement of ion activity. The variation of clay ionisation with concentration is not known to follow any equation as the strong electrolytes do, nor do they behave like weak electrolytes as measurement of the so called 'Dissociation Constants' shows^{2,3}.

Loosjes⁴ deduced the following equation relating to pH with clay concentration of hydrogen clay suspension

$$pH = \frac{K}{C+K} (pH_0 - pH_\alpha) + pH_\alpha \quad \dots (1)$$

where C is the clay concentration in any arbitrary unit, K is a constant. pH_0 and pH_α are extrapolated values obtained from a series of measurements. The applicability of this equation to Na- and Ca-clays has been studied in this paper. For this purpose, ion activities of H-clay, Na-clay and Ca-clay suspensions isolated from Jabalpur soil and Bihar bentonite have been determined at various clay concentrations.

The ion activity measurements were done with the help of resin membrane electrodes and checked with the glass electrode in the case of H-ion activity and with the clay membrane electrodes in the cases of Na⁺ and Ca⁺² ion activities.

EXPERIMENTAL

The clays ($< 0.05\mu$) were converted into their H-, Na- and Ca- forms by the usual procedure. The c.e.c.'s were determined by saturated NaCl-NaOH method using bromothymol blue as indicator. The c.e.c. of Jabalpur H-clay is 93 milli equivalent per 100 gms and that of Bihar bentonite is 100 milli equivalent per 100 gms of clay.

The resin membrane electrodes prepared in the usual way were obtained through the courtesy of Dr. Calmon of Ionac Chemical Company, Birmingham. The clay suspensions were diluted with double distilled water to the desired concentrations and equilibrated for

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4. H. R. Kruyt, *Colloid Science*, 1952, **1**, 186.

seven days, after which the cationic activities were measured according to usual procedure by using the appropriate membrane electrodes.

Both the inner reference solution and the outer clay suspensions were replaced by fresh solutions and a series of values were taken before recording the o.m.f's, care being taken to attain equilibrium, particularly in the case of Ca^{+2} ion activity measurement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I shows the measured pH with the corresponding concentration. Fig. 1 gives the graph (1) of pH with concentration from which the values of pH_0 and pH_α of equation (1) are measured and given in the same table. K given in the table is calculated on the basis of the relation that $K = C$ corresponding to $(pH_0 + pH_\alpha)/2$. It is observed that the equation (1) is valid upto 1.5% suspension in the case of Jabalpur H-clay but only upto 0.35% in the case of Bihar bentonite. Beyond these concentrations the calculated pH 's are higher than the observed as shown (Table I).

TABLE I

Hydrogen ion activity measurement

Conc. of Jabalpur H-Clay (%)	pH (obs)	pH (Calc)	ΔpH (2-3)
		$pH_\alpha = 2.77$ $pH_0 = 4.6$ $K = 0.2$ Obtained from the graph (1) in fig (1)	
	2	3	4
1.85	2.90	2.95	-0.05
1.32	3.03	3.01	+ .02
1.05	3.10	3.07	+ .03
0.73	3.20	3.17	+ .03
0.27	3.57	3.56	+ .01
0.16	3.78	3.79	- .01
0.11	3.96	3.97	.01
0.07	4.11	4.11	0
0.03	4.27	4.27	0
Bihar Bentonite H-Clay		$pH_\alpha = 3.28$ $pH_0 = 4.1$ $K = 0.2$	ΔpH
0.33	3.55	3.59	-0.04
0.27	3.62	3.63	-0.01
0.13	3.78	3.77	+ .01
0.08	3.90	3.87	+ .03
0.05	3.94	3.93	+ .01
0.02	4.00	4.00	0

TABLE II

Sodium ion activity measurement

Conc. of Jabalpur Na-Clay (%)	pNa (obs.)	pNa (Calc.)	ΔpNa (2—3)
		$pNa\alpha = 2.88$ $pNa_0 = 3.75$ $K = 0.29$ Obtained from the graph (2) in figure (1)	
	2	3	4
0.90	2.98	3.01	— .03
0.64	3.15	3.15	0
0.51	3.18	3.19	—0.01
0.26	3.33	3.34	—0.01
0.15	3.48	3.44	+0.04
0.05	3.65	3.62	+ .03
Bihar Bentonite Na-Clay		$pNa\alpha = 3.02$ $pNa_0 = 3.61$ $K = 0.20$	
0.44	3.15	3.20	—0.05
0.37	3.20	3.23	— .03
0.30	3.23	3.26	—0.03
0.22	3.30	3.30	0
0.15	3.42	3.36	+ .06
0.07	3.50	3.45	+ .05
0.03	3.55	3.55	0

TABLE III

Calcium ion activity measurement

Conc. of Jabalpur Ca-Clay (%)	pCa (obs.)	pCa (Calc.)	ΔpCa (2—3)
		$pCa\alpha = 3.48$ $pCa_0 = 4.54$ $K = 0.24$ Obtained from the graph (3) in figure (1)	
	2	3	4
0.24	4.01	4.00	+0.01
0.16	4.16	4.11	+ .05
0.04	4.38	4.38	0
0.02	4.44	4.45	—0.01
Bihar Bentonite Ca-Clay		$pCa\alpha = 3.60$ $pCa_0 = 4.80$ $K = 0.20$	
0.96	3.80	3.81	—0.01
0.64	3.90	3.38	+0.02
0.32	4.10	4.06	+0.04
0.13	4.33	4.33	0
0.06	4.53	4.51	+0.02
0.03	4.64	4.63	+0.01

Tables II and III show similar data with the Na- and Ca- systems respectively, calculated from graphs (2) and (3) in Fig. 1. It is observed that eqn. (1) is obeyed by Na- forms of Jabalpur clay upto 0.7% and of Bihar bontonite upto 0.4% concentrations. (1) In the case of Ca-forms of both Jabalpur and Bihar bentonite the equation holds good upto 1.0%.

FIG(1)

Chatterjee⁵ working with bivalent clays explained the differences in the cationic activities at comparable concentrations by referring to ion hydration. Mitra⁶ applying Ostowald's dilution law found no constant value of "Dissociation constant" for H-clays and concluded that H⁺ ions are held by the clay surface with different bonding energies.

According to Marshall⁷ variation in the mean free bonding energies of cation can be linked with many aspects of the chemistry of clay surfaces particularly regarding the surface dissociation. From the measurement of chemical potential of the cations in presence of clay, he concluded that different clays are dissociated to different degrees.

The deviation from eqn. (1) at higher concentration appears to be caused by an overlapping of the double layer associated with the colloidal particles and consequent "immobilisation" of the ions, so to say, and lowering of ionic activity. Mukherjee⁸ recorded a similar observation in the case of H-clays and Whitney and Peach⁹ in the case of Na-clays. At low moisture contents therefore the availability of nutrient ions is likely to be lowered, assuming that through an ion exchange process does the plant take up nutrient ions.

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